

COMPLEX COMPOUNDS OF BIGUANIDE WITH TERVALENT METALS. PART VI. COBALTIC TRISBIGUANIDINES.

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Tervalent cobalt has been found to combine with biguanide to form complex cobaltic trisbiguanidine, its hydrate and a series of well-defined salts, resembling the corresponding chromium complex and its derivatives in composition and properties.

With the exception of a cobaltic *ortho*-phenylenebiguanide compound (Ziegelbauer, *Monatsh*, 1896, 17, 648; Dubsky, Langer and Strand, *Collection*, 1938, 10, 112), no other complex biguanide compound of tervalent cobalt, either with simple or substituted biguanide, has been described in literature. In previous communications of this series (Rây and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 670; 1938, 15, 353, 633; Rây and Ghosh, *ibid.*, 1938, 15, 347, 350) complex compounds of tervalent chromium with simple and phenyl biguanide have been described and the constitution of the metallic biguanide complexes in general has been discussed. Study of the complex compounds of tervalent cobalt with simple biguanide—cobaltic trisbiguanidines—forms the subject matter of this communication.

Cobaltic trisbiguanide complexes closely resemble the corresponding chromium compounds in their composition and also in their physical and chemical properties. Like chromium, cobalt also forms an anhydrous trisbiguanidine, but gives rise to a solid dihydrated base, while the corresponding chromium compound is monohydrated. In solution both behave as triacidic base corresponding to the composition of their salts. The colour of cobaltic trisbiguanide compounds simulates those of its chromium analogues, except that the latter are more brightly coloured. The solubility of the two series of compounds runs in a parallel course, the chromium compounds being comparatively less soluble. The cobaltic biguanide complexes are, however, relatively much more stable than their chromium counterparts, and do not hydrolyse like the latter to form bisbiguanide derivatives in any appreciable amount even at the boiling temperature in solution.

The constitution of the cobaltic trisbiguanide complexes may be represented like those of chromium by the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{X}_3$, where $\text{X} = \text{OH}$ or any univalent or its equivalent acid radical. The anions, as in the case of chromium, are derived from a secondary co-ordination by the free amino group at one end of each biguanide molecule, the amino group at the other end co-ordinating with the central cobalt atom. The hydrogen atom of one of the outer imino ($=\text{NH}$) groups in each biguanide molecule is replaced by the cobalt atom through the exercise of

its primary valency. In other words, the central cobalt atom, as already discussed in the case of chromium complexes (Rây and Saha, *loc. cit.*), forms a neutral inner metallic complex by co-ordinating with three bidentate biguanide molecules, the cationic character of which is due solely to the free amino groups of the latter.

The preparation and properties of the anhydrous cobaltic *trisbiguanidine*, its dihydrate and a series of salts in which the complex behaves as a triacidic base are described in this paper.

The nature of its constitution as a hexa-co-ordinated complex with three bidentate molecules suggests at once the possibility of resolution into optically active modifications. In the case of chromium *trisbiguanide* compounds attempts at such resolution failed due to their more or less rapid hydrolysis into *bisbiguanide* derivatives. The stability of the cobaltic *trisbiguanide* complexes presents, however, a very favourable case for such resolution, and we have actually succeeded in preparing both the *dextro*- and *lacro*- series of these complexes. These will be reported in our next communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Cobaltic trisBiguanide Dihydrate.—A solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (5g.) was added to a solution of biguanide sulphate (17 g.) in strong alkali, when the yellow cobaltous biguanide was precipitated. This was oxidised by passing a vigorous current of air for 5-6 hours into the alkaline suspension. More alkali solution was added from time to time when the whole mass turned deep red with the formation of cobaltic biguanide in quantities. The mixture was then cooled and filtered on the pump. The crystals were purified by recrystallisation from slightly alkaline hot water. These were then dried in air, free from CO_2 . {Found : N, 53.0, 53.22; Co, 14.97. $[\text{Co}(\text{Big})_3] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 53.16; Co, 14.93 per cent} where $\text{BigH} = \text{one biguanide molecule}$.

The substance forms beautiful dark red crystals, which are moderately soluble in water giving a strongly alkaline solution. It liberates ammonia from ammonium salts, precipitates hydroxides of heavy metals from solutions of their salts, and behaves as a triacidic base in aqueous solution.

0.4056 G. of the substance in aqueous solution required 6.95 c.c. of 0.451N- H_2SO_4 for neutralisation. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] (\text{OH})_3$ requires 6.85 c.c.

Measurement of the equivalent conductivity and the determination of the freezing point of the solution of the base also lead to the same conclusion.

Equivalent Conductivity at 25°.

v (dilution) ...	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_v ...	25.9	33.9	44.2	55.4	66.6	76.6	92.0

Cryoscopic Measurement.

Subs. (g./100 c.c.)	Depression. Δ	Mol. wt. m .	van't Hoff's factor $i = M/m$.	Degree of dissociation. $\alpha = i - 1/n - 1$.
0.2671	0.041°	114.5	3.6	0.87

Where M = mol. wt. calculated as trihydrated base, n = no. of ions = 4.

The above results indicate that the substance is as strong a base as the alkali metal hydroxides.

Definite evidence regarding the triacidic nature of the base is, however, furnished by the preparation of a series of crystalline salts as described hereafter, in which one molecule of the base is found to combine with three equivalents of the acid. The determination of the valency of the complex ion by means of Ostwald-Walden's rule from the measurement of the equivalent conductivity of its hydrochloride furnishes additional proof thereto.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidine.—The dihydrate described above, when heated to 120-122° for some time, lost 9.057% of its weight. Percentage of water in the dihydrate is 9.1. The substance decomposes at higher temperatures. {Found: N, 58.20. [Co(Big)₃] requires N, 58.49 per cent}. The anhydrous base is dull red in colour and readily absorbs water.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride was prepared by treating the solid base in a mortar with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid till the mixture gave a slightly acid reaction. The yellow crystals formed, were filtered and washed with a little ice-cold water. These were purified by recrystallisation from hot water. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water, then with absolute alcohol and afterwards dried in air. The yellow crystals of the chloride are readily soluble in water. {Found: N, 45.03; Cl, 23.0, 23.12; Co, 12.69, 12.60. [Co(BigH⁺)₃]Cl₃ requires N, 44.85; Cl, 22.88; Co, 12.67 per cent}.

Equivalent Conductivity at 25°.

v (dilution) ...	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024
λ_c ...	90.7	101.1	110.0	116.8	123.3	126.5	130.6
λ_a ...	138.0	138.0	138.5	138.0	139.0	138.0	139.0

Mean $\lambda_a = 138.5$.

The λ_{∞} was calculated from Walden's formula,

$\lambda_{\infty} = \lambda_v (1 + n_1 n_2 \times 0.692 v^{-\frac{1}{2}})$; where v = dilution, n_1 and n_2 are the valencies of the ions.

The valency of the complex ion according to Ostwald-Walden's rule is given by $\lambda_{1024} - \lambda_{32} = 130.6 - 101.1 = 29.5 = 10 \times 2.95$. The valency is, therefore, three.

Cryoscopic Measurement.

Determination of the molecular weight by the freezing point method leads also to the same conclusion.

Subs. (g./100 c.c.).	Depression. Δ	Mol. wt. m	van't Hoff's factor. $i = M/m$.	Degree of dissociation. $\alpha = i - 1/n - 1$.
0.5784	0.088°	118.3	3.96	0.98

The result shows that even at 0° the substance dissociates almost completely into four ions and all the chlorine are present as ions.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium fluoride was obtained as soluble yellow crystals by adding a concentrated solution of ammonium fluoride to a strongly cooled, concentrated solution of the chloride. The crystals were washed and dried as described above. {Found: F, 13.31; Co, 14.0. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{F}_3$ requires F, 13.70; Co, 14.18 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium bromide was obtained in the form of bright yellow crystals by precipitating a solution of the chloride with a strong solution of potassium bromide. {Found: Br, 40.05; Co, 9.88. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{Br}_3$ requires Br, 40.07; Co, 9.83 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium iodide was obtained as yellow crystals from chloride and potassium iodide. It is less soluble than the other halides. {Found: I, 51.13; Co, 8.0. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{I}_3$ requires I, 51.48; Co, 7.97 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium thiocyanate was obtained in the form of reddish yellow crystals, soluble in water, by the double decomposition of the complex chloride and ammonium thiocyanate. It can also be prepared by heating a strong solution of the complex base with ammonium thiocyanate. {Found: S, 18.02; Co, 11.07. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] (\text{SCN})_3$ requires S, 17.91; Co, 11.07 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chlorate was prepared by precipitating a strong solution of the complex chloride with a saturated solution of potassium chlorate. It forms yellow crystals, moderately soluble in water. {Found: Cl, 17.40; Co, 9.59. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] (\text{ClO}_4)_3$ requires Cl, 17.47; Co, 9.68 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Perchlorate.—The readily soluble, orange-yellow crystals of the perchlorate were obtained by treating the finely powdered solid base in a mortar with a cold strong solution of perchloric acid. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: Cl, 16.10; Co, 8.98. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{ClO}_4)_3$ requires Cl, 16.19; Co, 8.98 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium borofluoride was prepared by heating a strong solution of the complex base with a concentrated solution of ammonium borofluoride till there was no further evolution of ammonia. The substance forms reddish yellow crystals, soluble in water. {Found: Co, 9.39. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{BF}_4)_3$ requires Co, 9.51 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium nitrate was obtained as orange-yellow crystals by neutralising the base with cold dilute nitric acid. The crystals were washed at first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. These were afterwards dried in air. The crystals are readily soluble in water. {Found: Co, 10.65; NO_3 , 34.01. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{NO}_3)_3$ requires Co, 10.83; NO_3 , 34.13 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium nitrite was prepared by precipitating a strong solution of the complex chloride with a cold concentrated solution of potassium nitrite. It forms orange-yellow crystals, soluble in water. {Found: N (nitritic), 8.41; Co, 11.80. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{NO}_2)_3$ requires N (nitritic), 8.45; Co, 11.87 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloro-carbonate.—When a strong solution of sodium carbonate was added to a cold concentrated solution of the complex chloride, the orange-yellow crystals of the chloro-carbonate separated from the solution. The mixture was cooled in ice and the crystals that finally separated were washed and dried as usual. The substance is readily soluble in water, the solution being strongly alkaline to litmus. {Found: C, 16.80; Cl, 15.20; Co, 12.60. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 \begin{matrix} \text{CO}_3 \\ \text{Cl}_4 \end{matrix}$ requires C, 16.85; Cl, 15.43; Co, 12.82 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Carbonate.—The neutral carbonate was prepared by adding three molecular proportions of sodium bicarbonate to a cold concentrated solution of the complex base. The mixture was cooled in ice and the normal carbonate was salted out by the addition of a saturated solution of sodium carbonate. The crystals were washed and dried as before. The substance forms orange-yellow crystals, readily soluble in water, the solution being strongly alkaline to litmus. {Found: C, 18.50; Co, 12.12. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{CO}_3)_3$ requires C, 18.55; Co, 12.16 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium sulphate was obtained in the form of sparingly soluble light red flakes when a solution of ammonium sulphate was added to that of the complex chloride. {Found: N, 37.09; S, 8.46;

Co, 10.40. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 37.11; S, 8.48; Co, 10.42 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium selenate was obtained as moderately soluble light red flakes by treating the solid powdered base in a mortar with a cold solution of selenic acid. The crystals were filtered, washed with ice-water and then dried in air. {Found: Co, 9.21; Se, 18.51. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{SeO}_4)_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 9.26; Se, 18.65 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium Chloro-selenate.—A cold saturated solution of the complex chloride was treated with a strong solution of potassium selenate. The mixture was strongly cooled and the precipitated crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: Cl, 6.0; Co, 10.0; Se, 13.25. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \frac{\text{Cl}}{\text{SeO}_4}$ requires Cl, 6.0; Co, 9.97; Se, 13.35 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium dithionate was precipitated in the form of light red flakes when a cold saturated solution of the complex chloride was treated with a strong solution of sodium dithionate. The substance is moderately soluble in water. {Found: S, 15.84; Co, 9.85. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{S}_2\text{O}_8)_3$ requires S, 16.03; Co, 9.85 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium Hydroxo-sulphite.—When a freshly prepared solution of sodium bisulphite was added, drop by drop, to an ice-cold concentrated solution of the base until the latter was partially neutralised, orange-yellow crystals of the hydroxo-sulphite separated from the solution. The crystals are moderately soluble in water giving an alkaline solution. {Found: S, 6.72; Co, 12.0. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \frac{\text{OH}}{\text{SO}_3}$ requires S, 6.50; Co, 12.0 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium Sulphite.—The normal sulphite was obtained as a reddish yellow crystalline precipitate by adding a freshly prepared concentrated solution of sodium sulphite to the cold concentrated solution of the complex chloride. The mixture was cooled in ice for some time and the crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: S, 8.74; Co, 10.68. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2(\text{SO}_3)_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires S, 8.85; Co, 10.88 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloro-thiosulphate was precipitated in the form of sparingly soluble orange-coloured, silky crystals by the addition of a solution of sodium thiosulphate to that of the complex chloride. {Found: Cl, 6.24; S, 11.63; Co, 10.65. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \frac{\text{Cl}}{\text{S}_2\text{O}_3} \cdot 2\frac{1}{2}\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 6.43; S, 11.60; Co, 10.65 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium Thiosulphate.—When a solution of the complex base was mixed with a solution of sodium thiosulphate and to the mixture a solution of ammonium acetate was added, light red silky crystals

of the normal thiosulphate were precipitated. {Found: S, 18'15; Co, 11'10. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{S}_2\text{O}_3)_2$ requires S, 18'21; Co, 11'19 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloro-chromate was obtained as a dark yellow crystalline precipitate when a solution of potassium chromate was added to that of the complex chloride. The crystals were washed with ice-water and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . {Found: Cl, 6'81; Co, 11'52; Cr, 10'48. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{CrO}_4$ requires Cl, 6'95; Co, 11'55; Cr, 11'20 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chromate.—When a solution of potassium dichromate was added to a solution of the complex base in the cold, sparingly soluble yellowish brown crystals of the normal chromate separated out. These were washed with cold water and dried in air. {Found: Co, 10'50; Cr, 13'72. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{CrO}_4)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10'53; Cr, 13'92 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Perchromate.—When ammoniacal hydrogen peroxide (perhydrol) was added to a cold mixture of potassium chromate and the complex base in solution, dark yellowish brown crystals of the perchromate separated out after a short time. The crystals were washed with ice-cold water and dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 . {Found: Co, 9'57; Cr, 8'47; O, 11'4 (gasometrically), 12'4 (on correcting for chromate left in the solution after the evolution of oxygen). $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{CrO}_8 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 9'65; Cr, 8'47; O, 13'0 per cent}.

The perchromate decomposes, when acidified, giving rise to a blue solution; the blue colour disappears rapidly with the formation of green chromic salt.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloro-phosphate was obtained as a sparingly soluble, flesh-coloured crystalline precipitate by adding a solution of disodium hydrogen phosphate to a solution of the complex chloride. The crystals were washed first with cold water, then with alcohol and afterwards dried in air. {Found: Cl, 7'10; Co, 12'0; P, 6'35. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3] \text{HPO}_4$ requires Cl, 7'23; Co, 12'02; P, 6'33 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium phosphate was obtained as a light red powder by precipitating a solution of the complex base with a solution of disodium hydrogen phosphate. {Found: Co, 10'61; P, 8'24. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{HPO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 10'58; P, 8'34 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium hydrosulphide was prepared by passing H_2S into a well-cooled slightly ammoniacal solution of the complex base. The precipitate formed was filtered and washed with ice-cold water. The substance decomposes on drying.

An analysis of the moist substance by oxidation with bromine gave: CoSO_4 , 0.1360 g.; BaSO_4 , 0.6057 g. Hence $\text{Co} : \text{S} = 1 : 3$. The molecular formula is, therefore, represented by $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{HS})_3$.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium hydro-polysulphide was obtained as a sparingly soluble crystalline precipitate by adding a solution of the yellow ammonium sulphide to that of the complex base. The crystals were washed at first with ice-cold water, then with alcohol and afterwards dried in vacuum over concentrated H_2SO_4 . {Found: S, 34.58; Co, 10.60. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{HS}_2)_3$ requires S, 34.65; Co, 10.65 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium iodate was prepared by treating the well-powdered complex base with a solution of iodic acid in a mortar. The reddish yellow crystals were filtered, washed and dried in air. The substance is fairly soluble in water. {Found: I, 42.93; Co, 6.61. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{IO}_3)_3$ requires I, 43.09; Co, 6.65 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloro-iodate was obtained as a yellow crystalline precipitate by treating a solution of the complex chloride with that of sodium iodate. The crystals were washed and dried as usual. {Found: Cl, 7.96; I, 27.34; Co, 8.41. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 \cdot \text{Cl}_3 \cdot (\text{IO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cl, 7.74; I, 27.86; Co, 8.62 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium periodate was obtained by precipitation from a solution of the complex chloride with sodium periodate. {Found: I (periodic), 20.42; Co, 9.50. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 \text{IO}_5 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires I, 20.48; Co, 9.51 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium Oxalate.—Reddish yellow, fairly soluble crystals of the oxalate were obtained by treating the complex base with a cold concentrated solution of oxalic acid. {Found: Co, 12.0; C_2O_4 , 26.50. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3$ requires Co, 12.01; C_2O_4 , 26.88 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium camphorsulphonate was obtained as a flesh-coloured, moderately soluble crystalline precipitate by neutralising a cold concentrated solution of the complex base with a cold strong solution of camphorsulphonic acid. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. They were dried over concentrated H_2SO_4 in vacuum. {Found: S, 9.12; Co, 5.71. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_3](\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{15}\text{OSO}_3)_3$ requires S, 9.20; Co, 5.61 per cent}.